

1 Color Constancy algorithms: psychophysical evaluation on a 2 new dataset

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7 **Abstract**

8

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10 *vision. Color constancy algorithms have dealt with this problem by defining different heuristics to select a unique solution*
11 *from within the feasible set. The performance of these algorithms has shown that there is still a long way to go to globally*
12 *solve this problem as a preliminary step in computer vision. In general, performance evaluation has been done by*
13 *comparing the angular error between the estimated chromaticity and the chromaticity of a canonical illuminant, which is*
14 *highly dependent on the image dataset. Recently, some workers have used high-level constraints to estimate illuminants; in*
15 *this case selection is based on increasing the performance on the subsequent steps of the systems. In this paper we propose*
16 *a new performance measure, the perceptual angular error. It evaluates the performance of a color constancy algorithm*
17 *according to the perceptual preferences of humans, or naturalness (instead of the actual optimal solution) and is*
18 *independent of the visual task. We show the results of a new psychophysical experiment comparing solutions from three*
19 *different color constancy algorithms. Our results show that in more than a half of the judgments the preferred solution is*
20 *not the one closest to the optimal solution. Our experiments were performed on a new dataset of images acquired with a*
21 *calibrated camera with an attached neutral grey sphere, which better copes with the illuminant variations of the scene.*

22

23 **Keywords:** Color Constancy evaluation, Psychophysics, Computational Color.

24

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48 1. Introduction

49

50 Color Constancy is the ability of the human visual system to perceive a stable representation of color despite illumination
51 changes. Like other perceptual constancy capabilities of the visual system, color constancy is crucial for succeeding in many
52 ecologically relevant visual tasks such as food collection, detection of predators, etc. The importance of color constancy in biological
53 vision is mirrored in computer vision applications, where success in a wide range of visual tasks relies on achieving a high degree of

54 illuminant invariance. In the last twenty years, research in computational color constancy has tried to recover the illuminant of a
55 scene from an acquired image

56 This has been shown to be a mathematically ill-posed problem which therefore does not have a unique solution. A common
57 computational approach to illuminant recovery (and color constancy in general) is to produce a list of possible illuminants (feasible
58 solutions) and then use some assumptions, based on the interactions of scene surfaces and illuminants to select the most appropriate
59 solution among all possible illuminants. A recent extended review of computational color constancy methods was provided by
60 Hordley¹. In this review, computational algorithms were classified in five different groups according to how they approach the
61 problem. These were (a) simple statistical methods², (b) neural networks³, (c) gamut mapping^{4,5}, (d) probabilistic methods⁶ and (e)
62 physics-based methods⁷. Comparison studies^{8,9} have ranked the performance of these algorithms, which usually depend on the
63 properties of the image dataset and the statistical measures used for the evaluation. It is generally agreed that, although some
64 algorithms may perform well in average, they may also perform poorly for specific images. This is the reason why some authors¹⁰
65 have proposed a one-to-one evaluation of the algorithms on individual images. In this way, comparisons become more independent
66 of the chosen image dataset. However, the general conclusion is that more research should be directed towards a combination of
67 different methods, since the performance of a method usually depends on the type of scene it deals with¹¹. Recently, some interesting
68 studies have pointed out towards this direction¹², i.e. trying to find which statistical properties of the scenes determine the best color
69 constancy method to use. In all these approaches, the evaluation of the performance of the algorithms has been based on computing
70 the *angular error* between the selected solution and the actual solution that is provided by the acquisition method.

71 Other recent proposals^{13,14} turn away from the usual approach and deal instead with multiple solutions delegating the selection
72 of a unique solution to a subsequent step that depends on high-level, task-related interpretations, such as the ability to annotate the
73 image content. In this example, the best solution would be the one giving the best semantic annotation of the image content. It is in
74 this kind of approach where the need for a different evaluation emerges, since the performance depends on the visual task and this
75 can lead to an inability to compare different methods. Hence, to be able to evaluate this performance and to compare it with other
76 high-level methods, we propose to explore a new evaluation procedure.

77 In summary, the goal of this paper is to show the results of a new psychophysical experiment following the lines of that
78 presented in¹⁵. The previous results were confirmed, that is, humans do not chose the minimum angular error solution as the more
79 natural. Furthermore, in this paper we propose a new measure to reduce the gap between the error measure and the Humans
80 preference. Our new experiment represents an improvement over the old one in that it considers the uncertainty level of the observer
81 responses and it uses a new, improved image dataset. This new dataset has been built by using a neutral gray sphere attached to the
82 calibrated camera to better estimate the illuminant of the scene. We have worked with the shades-of-grey¹⁶ algorithm instead of
83 CRule¹⁷. This decision has been taken on the basis of CRule is calibrated whereas the other algorithms are not. This paper is divided
84 as follows. In section 2 we present how the experiment has been driven. Afterwards, in section 3 we show the results. Later on, in
85 section 4 a new perceptual measure to deal with the evaluation of color constancy algorithms is presented. Finally, in section 5, we
86 sum up the conclusions.

87

88 **2. Experimental Setup**

89 Subjects were presented with a pair of images (each one a different color constancy solution) on a CRT monitor and asked to
90 select the image that seems "most natural". The term "natural" was chosen not because it refers to natural objects but because it refers
91 to natural viewing conditions, implying the least amount of digital manipulation or global perception of an illuminant. Figure 1
92 shows some exemplary pictures from the database. The pictures on the left are examples of images selected as natural most of the
93 time, while those on the right are examples of images hardly ever selected as natural.

94

95

96 *Figure 1: Images regularly selected in the experiment as natural (left) versus images hardly ever selected (right).*

97 The global schematics of the experiment are shown in Figure 2. We used a set of 83 images from a new image dataset that was
98 built for this experiment (the image gathering details are explained in section 2.2). The camera calibration allows us to obtain the
99 CIE1931 XYZ values for each pixel and consequently, we converted 83 images from CIE XYZ space to CIE sRGB. Following this,
100 we replaced the original illuminant by D65 using the chromaticity values of the grey sphere that was present in all image scenes.

101

102 From the original images, 5 new pictures were created by re-illuminating the scene with 5 different illuminants. To this end we
103 have used the chromatic values of each illuminant (3 Plankians: 4000K, 7000K, 10000K, and two arbitrary illuminants: Greenish (x
104 $= 0.3026$, $y = 0.3547$) and Purplish ($x = 0.2724$, $y = 0.2458$), totaling 415 images. Afterwards, the three color constancy algorithms
105 (Grey-World², Shades-of-Grey¹⁶ and MaxName¹⁵) explained in section 2.2 were applied to the newly created images. Consequently,
106 we obtain one solution per test image per algorithm, totaling 1245 different solutions. These solutions were converted back to CIE
107 XYZ to be displayed on a calibrated CRT monitor (Viewsonic P227f, which was tested to confirm its uniformity across the screen
108 surface) using a visual stimulus generator (Cambridge Research Systems ViSaGe). The monitor's white point chromaticity was
109 ($x=0.315$, $y= 0.341$) and its maximum luminance was 123.78 Cd/m^2 . The experiment was conducted in a dark room (i.e. the only
110 light present in the room came from the monitor itself).

111

112 *Figure 2: Experiment Schedule.*

113 The experiment was conducted on 10 naïve observers recruited among university students and staff (none of the observers had
 114 previously seen the picture database). All observers were tested for normal color vision using the Ishihara and the Farnsworth
 115 Dichotomous Test (D-15). Pairs of pictures (each obtained using one of two different color constancy algorithms) were presented one
 116 on top of the other on a grey background (31 Cd/m²). The order and position of the picture pairs was random. Each picture subtended
 117 10.5 x 5.5 degrees to the observer and was viewed from 146 cm. This brings us to 1245 pairs of observations per observer. No
 118 influence on picture (top or bottom) position in the observers' decision was found.

119

120 For each presentation, observers were asked to select the picture that seemed most natural, and to rate their selection by pressing
 121 a button on an IR button box. The set up (six buttons) allowed observers to register how convinced they were of their choice (e.g.
 122 strongly convinced, convinced, and marginally convinced). For example if an observer was strongly convinced that the top image
 123 was more natural than the bottom one, it would press button 3 (see Figure 2), if it was marginally convinced that the bottom picture
 124 was the most natural it would press button 4 and so on. There was no time limit but observers took an average of 2.5 seconds to
 125 respond to each choice. The total experiment lasted 90 minutes approximately (divided in three sessions of 30 minutes each)

126 **2.1. A new image dataset**

127 To test the models we need a large image dataset of good quality natural scenes. From a colorimetric point of view, the obvious
 128 choice is to produce hyperspectral imagery, to reduce metameric effects. However, hyperspectral outdoor natural scenes are difficult
 129 to acquire since the exposure times needed are long and its capture implies control over small movements or changes in the scene,
 130 (not to talk of the financial cost of the equipment). There are currently good quality images databases available (such as the
 131 hyperspectral dataset built by Foster *et al*¹⁸ and Brelstaff *et al*¹⁹), but they either contain specialised (i.e. non-general) imagery or the
 132 number of scenes is not large enough for our purposes. For this reason, and because metamerism is relatively rare in natural

133 scenes^{20,21}, we decided to acquire our own dataset of 83 images (see Figure 3) using a trichromatic digital colour camera (Sigma
134 Foveon D10) calibrated to produce CIEXYZ pixel representations.

135 The camera was calibrated at Bristol University (UK) Experimental Psychology lab by measuring its color sensors' spectral
136 sensitivities using a set of 31 spectrally narrowband interference filters, a constant-current incandescent light source and a TopCon
137 SR1 telespectroradiometer (a process similar to that by others^{22,23}). The calibrated camera allows us to obtain a measure of the CIE
138 XYZ values for every pixel in the image. Images were acquired around Barcelona city at different times of the day and in three
139 different days in July 2008. The weather was mostly sunny with a few clouds. We mounted a grey ball in front of the camera (see
140 Figure 4), following the ideas of Ciurea *et al*²⁴. The ball was uniformly painted using several thin layers of spray paint (Revell
141 RAL7012-Matt, whose reflectance was approximately constant across the camera's response spectrum and its reflective properties
142 were nearly Lambertian –see Figure 5). The presence of the grey ball (originally located at the bottom-left corner of every picture and
143 subsequently cropped out) allows us to measure and manipulate the color of the illuminant. Images whose chromaticity distribution
144 was not spatially uniform (as measured on the grey ball) were discarded.

145
146

147
148 *Figure 3: Image dataset under D65 illuminant.*

149
150 *Figure 4: Camera and grey sphere setup.*

151

152 *Figure 5: Reflectance of the paint used on the ball.*

153 **2.2. Selected color constancy algorithms**

154

155 In this section we briefly summarize the three methods we have selected for our analysis. We have chosen two well-known
 156 methods, Grey-World² and Shades-of-Grey¹⁶, and a more recent method, the MaxName algorithm¹⁵. The Grey-World algorithm (an
 157 uncalibrated method based on a strong assumption about the scene) was selected because of its popularity in the literature. The
 158 Shades-of-Grey algorithm (another uncalibrated algorithm) was selected because it considerably improves performance with respect
 159 to Grey-World (another uncalibrated algorithm such as Grey-edge²⁵ could also have been used). Finally, MaxName¹⁵ was selected
 160 because it uses high-level knowledge to correct the illuminant. We give a brief outline of these methods below.

161 **1. Grey-World.** It was proposed by Bunschbaum² and it is based on the hypothesis that mean chromaticity of the scene
 162 corresponds to grey. Given an image $f = (R,G,B)^T$ as a function of RGB values, and adopting the diagonal model of illuminant
 163 change²⁶, then an illuminant (α,β,γ) accomplishes the Grey-World hypothesis if

164

165
$$\frac{\int f \partial x}{\int \partial x} = k \cdot (\alpha, \beta, \gamma) \quad (1)$$

166

167 where k is a constant.

168

169 **2. Shades-of-grey.** It was proposed by Finlayson¹⁶. This algorithm is a statistical extension of Grey-World and MaxRGB²⁷
 170 algorithms. It is based on Minkowski norm of images. An illuminant (α,β,γ) is considered as the scene illuminant if it accomplishes

171
$$\left(\frac{\int f^p \partial x}{\int \partial x} \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} = k \cdot (\alpha, \beta, \gamma) \quad (2)$$

172 where k is a constant. Actually, this is a family of methods where $p=1$ is Grey-World method, and $p= \infty$ is Max-RGB algorithm.

173 In this case we have used $p= 12$, since it is the best solution for our dataset.

174

175 **3. MaxName.** This algorithm is a particular case of the one presented by Vazquez *et al*¹⁵. It is based on giving more weight to
 176 those illuminants that maximize the number of color names in the scene. That is, MaxName builds a weighted feasible set by
 177 considering *nameable* colors, this is prior knowledge given by

$$179 \quad \mu_k = \int_{\omega} S(\lambda)E(\lambda)R_k(\lambda)\partial\lambda \quad , k=R, G, B \quad (3)$$

180
 181 where, $S(\lambda)$ are the surface reflectances having maximum probability of being labeled with a basic color term, also called focal
 182 reflectances (from the work of Benavente²⁸). In addition to the basic color terms, we added a set of skin colored reflectances. In
 183 Equation 3, $E(\lambda)$ is the power distribution of a D65 illuminant and $R_k(\lambda)$ are the CIE RGB 1955 Color Matching Functions.

184 We define μ as the set of all k-dimensional *nameable* colors obtained from Equation 3. The number of elements of μ depends on
 185 the number of reflectances used. Following this, we compute the *Semantic Matrix*, denoted as SM , which is a binary representation of
 186 the color space as a matrix, where a point is set to 1 if it represents a *nameable* color, that is, it belongs to μ , and 0 otherwise. Then,
 187 for a given input image, I , we compute all possible illuminant changes $I_{\alpha,\beta,\gamma}$. For each one, we calculate its *nameability* value. This is
 188 done by counting how many points of the mapped image are *nameable* colors in SM and can be computed by a correlation in log
 189 space:

$$190 \quad Nval_{\alpha,\beta,\gamma} = \log(H_{bin}(I)) * \log(SM) \quad (4)$$

191
 192 In the previous equation, H_{bin} is the binarized histogram of the image, $Nval$ at the position (α,β,γ) is the number of
 193 coincidences between the SM and $I_{\alpha,\beta,\gamma}$. $Nval$ is a 3-dimensional matrix, depending on all the feasible maps, (α,β,γ) . From this
 194 matrix, we select the most feasible illuminant as the one that accomplishes:

$$196 \quad (\alpha, \beta, \gamma) = \arg \max_{(\alpha,\beta,\gamma)} Nval \quad (5)$$

197 that is, the one giving the maximum number of *nameable* colors.

198 **3. Results**

199
 200 The results of the experiment validate those presented by Vazquez *et al*¹⁵, with a different image dataset and a different set of
 201 algorithms. The main finding is that preferred solutions, namely the more natural in the psychophysical experiment, do not always
 202 coincide with solutions of minimum angular error. In fact, this agreement only happened in 43% of the observations, independently
 203 of the degree of certainty of the observers when making the decision.

204 Since the experimental procedure allows us to define a partition in the interval [0,1] to encode the subject selection and each
 205 observation represents a decision between two images, then for each observation we label one image as the result from Method A,

206 and the other as the result from Method B (Method A and B are labeled as 1 and 0, respectively). The confidence of the decision is
 207 considered at three different levels (the three buttons that the subject was allowed to press –ordinal paired comparison²⁹). For
 208 example, suppose that a scene processed by Method A is presented on top of the screen and a second scene processed by Method B is
 209 presented at the bottom (the physical position of the scenes was randomized in each trial, but let’s consider an exemplary layout). If
 210 the subject thinks that the top picture is more natural it will press one of the top buttons in Figure 2 according to how much he/she is
 211 convinced. Suppose the subject presses button 3 (top-right: definitely more natural), then the response is coded as 1. If the choice is
 212 button 2 (top-center: sufficiently more natural) the response is coded as 0.8, etc. (see Table 1). If, on the contrary the subject thinks
 213 the bottom picture (Method B) is more natural, then he/she will press a button from the lower row (Figure 2). If he/she is marginally
 214 convinced, will pick button 4 (bottom-left) and the response will be coded as 0.4 according to Table 1. Similarly if he/she is strongly
 215 convinced, will press button 6 (bottom-right) and the response will be coded as 0. In this way we collect not only the direction of the
 216 response but its certainty. Observer’s certainty was found to be correlated (corr. coef. 0.726) to a simple measure of image difference
 217 (the angular error between each image pair). This technique is similar to that used by other researchers³⁰⁻³³.

Image at the bottom is more “natural” than Image at the top			Image at the top is more “natural” than Image at the bottom		
Button 6	Button 5	Button 4	Button 1	Button 2	Button 3
Definitely more natural	Sufficiently more natural	Marginally more natural	Marginally more natural	Sufficiently more natural	Definitely more natural
0	0.2	0.4	0.6	0.8	1

218 *Table 1: Buttons codification.*

219
 220 We have computed two different measures of observer variability. The first measure is the correlation coefficient between
 221 individual subjects and the average (in black in Figure 6). Table 2 shows this measure. The idea behind this analysis is to detect
 222 outliers (subjects with a distribution of results significantly different to the rest of the observers, i.e. low correlation). Our second
 223 measure is the coefficient of variation (CV)^{34,35}, which computes the difference between two statistical samples (see Table 2). Both
 224 measures were calculated for the whole 1245 observations (3 combinations of color constancy solutions x 415 observations per
 225 combination).

226

227

228 *Figure 6: Comparison to the mean observer (black line).*

229

Observer	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Correlation	0.54	0.57	0.59	0.55	0.52	0.23	0.48	0.63	0.61	0.55
CV	52,49%	57,96%	37,65%	52,28%	52,69%	59,85%	47,12%	51,13%	25,36%	42,81%

230 *Table 2: Correlation between each observer and mean observer.*

231 From this table, and from the distribution of the plots in Figure 6, we decided to omit data from observer 6 (very low correlation
 232 coefficient and highest coefficient of variation) in all subsequent analysis.

233

234 As a first approach to analyze our results we computed the mean of the observers' responses for each pairwise comparison. We
 235 considered that a method was selected if the mean of the encoded decisions, computed for all 9 observers, is greater than 0.5 (when
 236 the method was encoded as 1) or lower than 0.5 (when the method was encoded as 0). The performance does not vary significantly if
 237 we do not consider the cases where the average value is too close to the chance rate (e.g. averages between 0.45 and 0.55). The
 238 results of these pairwise comparisons are given in Table 3. For each pair of methods, we show the percentage of cases where it has
 239 been selected against the others. Thus, results in Table 3 can be interpreted as follows: each method (in rows) is preferred a certain
 240 percentage of trials over the method in the columns. For example, Shades-of-Grey is preferred in 68.1% of the trials against Grey-
 241 world.

242

243

244

245

vs. Method	Shades-of-Grey	Grey-World	MaxName
Selected method			
Shades-of-Grey	-	68.1%	50.6%
Grey-World	31.9%	-	37.6%
MaxName	49.4%	62.4%	-

246 *Table 3: Results of the experiment in the 1-to-1 comparison.*

247 The percentages in Table 3 show that the images produced by Shades-of-Grey and MaxName are preferred to those produced by
 248 Grey-World (68,1% and 62,4%). However, there is no clear preference when compared against each other (50.6% Shades-of-Grey
 249 preference vs. MaxName).

250

251 In Table 4 we show a global comparison of all algorithms (the percentages are computed for all 415 images). A method was
 252 considered a “winner” for a given image if it was selected in two of the three comparisons. Methods were evaluated in the same way
 253 as we did for results in Table 3 (that is, a greater than a 0.5 mean value from all observers is encoded as 1). Evaluating this way, there
 254 are some cases where the three methods are equally selected (this happens in 8.92% of the images). This analysis was formulated in
 255 order to remove non-transitive comparisons (e.g. method A beats method B, method B beats method C and method C beats method
 256 A). Hence, we can conclude from these straightforward analyses that solutions from MaxName are preferred in general, but closely
 257 followed by Shades-of-Grey (39.28% and 35.18% respectively). We can also state that Grey-World solutions are the least preferred
 258 in general (with a low percentage of 16.63%). Moreover, the best angular error solution is selected in 42.96% of the cases.

259

Method	Wins
Shades-of-Grey	35.18%
Grey-World	16.63%
MaxName	39.28%
3-equally selected	8,92%

260 *Table 4: Experiment results in a general comparison.*

261 We have also calculated the Thurstone’s Law of Comparative Judgement³⁶ coefficients from our data (Table 5), obtained from
 262 the ordinal pairwise comparisons. Using this measure, results are not very different (Shades-of-Grey and Maxname are clearly better
 263 than Grey-World although the ranking changes) and images with minimal angular error are only selected in 45% of the cases.

264

Method	Wins
Shades-of-grey	42.65 %
MaxName	36.39 %
Grey-World	20.96 %

265 *Table 5: Results using Thurstone's Law of Comparative Judgement*

266 Finally, we have computed two overall analyses (considering all scenes as one) in order to extract a global ranking for our color
 267 constancy methods: the Thurstone's Law of Comparative Judgement³⁶ and the Bradley-Terry³⁷ analysis. Table 6 shows the results of
 268 the Bradley and Terry's cumulative logit model for pairwise evaluations extended to ordinal comparisons²⁹. These results are shown
 269 on the "estimate" column where the estimate reference has been set to 0 for the smallest value (Grey-World model). The standard
 270 error of this ranking measure shows that the two best models (Shades-of-Grey and MaxName) are better than Grey-World and
 271 arguably close to each other. Table 7 shows a similar analysis using Thurstone's Law of Comparative Judgement³⁶ and considering
 272 all scenes as one.

273

Parameter	DF	Estimate	Standard Error	Wald 95% Confidence Limits		Chi-Square	Pr>ChiSq
Shades-of-grey	1	1.609	1.2231	-0.7882	4.0063	1.73	0.1883
MaxName	1	1.0256	0.8435	-0.6278	2.6789	1.48	0.2241
Grey-World	0	0	0	0	0	.	.

274 *Table 6: Results using Bradley-Terry ordinal pairwise comparison analysis*

275

Parameter	DF	Estimate	Standard Error	Wald 95% Confidence Limits		Chi-Square	Pr>ChiSq
Shades-of-grey	1	0.196	0.0031	0.19	0.2021	4040.2	<.0001
MaxName	1	0.1283	0.0031	0.1223	0.1343	1743.22	<.0001
Grey-World	0	0	0	0	0	.	.

276 *Table 7: Results using Thurston law of comparative judgment binary pairwise comparison analysis*

277

278 As we mentioned above, our experiment shows that images having minimum angular error with respect to the canonical solution
 279 are selected in less than half of the observations (when we ask people for the most natural image, the response, does not always
 280 correspond to the optimal physical solution). Moreover, this result is maintained even if we discard responses with low levels of
 281 certainty. In order to quantify this fact, in the next section we will introduce a new measure to complement the current performance
 282 evaluation of color constancy algorithms.

283 **4. Perceptual performance evaluation**

284

285 Assuming the ill-posed nature of the problem, the difficulty of finding an optimal solution and the results of the present
286 experiment, we propose an approach to color constancy algorithms that involves human color constancy by trying to match
287 computational solutions to perceived solutions. Hence, we propose a new evaluation measurement, the *Perceptual Angular Error*,
288 which is based on perceptual judgments of adequacy of a solution instead of the physical solution. The approach that we propose in
289 this work does not try to give an alternative line research to the current trends which focus on classifying scene contents to efficiently
290 combine different methods: here we try to complement these efforts from a different point of view that we could consider as more
291 “top-down”, instead of the “bottom-up” nature of the usual research.

292 As mentioned before, the most common performance evaluation for color constancy algorithms consists in measuring how close
293 their proposed solution is to the physical solution, independently of the other concerns. This has been computed as

294

$$295 \quad e_{ang} = a \cos \left(\frac{\rho_w \hat{\rho}_w}{\|\rho_w\| \|\hat{\rho}_w\|} \right) \quad (6)$$

296

297 which represents the angle between the actual white point of the scene illuminant, ρ_w , and the estimation of this point given by the
298 color constancy method, $\hat{\rho}_w$, which can be understood as a chromaticity distance between the physical solution and the estimate.
299 The current consensus is that none of the current algorithms present a good performance on all the images³⁸, and a combination of
300 different algorithms offers a promising option for further research. Our proposal here is to introduce a new measure, the *perceptual*
301 *angular error*, e_{ang}^p , that would be computed in a similar way:

302

$$303 \quad e_{ang}^p = a \cos \left(\frac{\rho_w^p \hat{\rho}_w}{\|\rho_w^p\| \|\hat{\rho}_w\|} \right) \quad (7)$$

304

305 where ρ_w^p is the perceived white point of the scene (which should be measured psychophysically) and $\hat{\rho}_w$ is an estimation of this
306 point, that is the result of any color constancy method, as in Equation 6. The difficulty of this new measurement arises from the
307 complexity of building a large image dataset, where ρ_w^p , the perceived white point of the images has been measured.

308 In this work we propose a simple estimation of this perceived white point by considering the images preferred in the previous
309 experiment. Hence, the perceived white point is given by the images coming from the color constancy solutions that have been
310 preferred by the observers. The preferred solutions, that is, the most natural solutions, can give us an approximation to the perceived
311 image white point.

312 Making the above consideration, in Figure 7 we can see how the estimation of the perceptual angular error works for the three
 313 tested algorithms. In the abscissa we plot a ranking of the observations in order to get the perceptual errors in descending order. In
 314 the ordinate we show the estimated perceptual angular error for each created image (that is, 415 different inputs to the algorithms). A
 315 numerical estimation of the perceptual angular error could be the area under the curves plotted in Figure 7. In the figure we can see
 316 that both Shades-of-Grey and MaxName work quite similarly, while Grey-World presents the highest perceptual error. This new
 317 measurement agrees with the conclusion we summarized in the previous section and provides a complementary measure to evaluate
 318 color constancy algorithms. In Figure 8 we show a similar plot for the usual angular error.

319

320

321 *Figure 7: Estimated Perceptual Angular error (between method estimations and preferred illuminants).*

322

323 *Figure 8: Angular error between methods estimations and canonical illuminant.*

324 In Tables 8 and 9 we show the different statistics on the computed angular errors. In Table 8, the angular error between the
 325 estimated illuminant and the canonical illuminant are shown. In this case, MaxName and Shades-of-Grey present better results than

326 Grey-World. In Table 9 equal statistics are computed for the estimated perceptual angular error. The results on this table confirm the
327 conclusions we obtained from Figure 7.

328

	Mean	RMS	Median
MaxName	7.64°	8.84°	6.78°
Shades-of-Grey	7.84°	9.70°	5.95°
Grey-World	10.05°	12.70°	7.75°

329 *Table 8: Angular error for the different methods on 415 images of the dataset.*

330

	Mean	RMS	Median
MaxName	3.86°	6.02°	2.61°
Shades-of-Grey	3.79°	5.66°	2.86°
Grey-World	6.70°	9.01°	5.85°

331 *Table 9: Estimated perceptual angular error for the different methods on 415 images of the dataset.*

332 5. Conclusion

333

334 This paper explores a new research line, the psychophysical evaluation of color constancy algorithms. Previous research point
335 out to the need to further explore the behavior of high-level constraints needed for the selection of a feasible solution (to avoid the
336 dependency of current evaluations on the statistics of the image dataset). With this aim in mind, we have performed a psychophysical
337 experiment in order to compare three computational color constancy algorithms: Shades-of-Grey, Grey-World and MaxName. The
338 results of the experiment show Shades-of-grey and MaxName methods have quite similar results which are better than those obtained
339 by the Grey-World method and that in almost half of the judgments; subjects have preferred solutions that are not the closest ones to
340 the optimal solutions.

341 Considering that subjects do not prefer the optimal solutions in a large percentage of judgments; we have introduced a new
342 measure, based on the perceptual solutions to complement current evaluations: the Perceptual Angular Error. It tries to measure the
343 proximity of the computational solutions versus the human color constancy solutions. The current experiment allows computing an
344 estimation of the perceptual angular error for the three explored algorithms. However, our main conclusion is that further work
345 should be done in the line of building a large dataset of images linked to the perceptually preferred judgments.

346 To this end a new, more complex experiment, perhaps related to the one proposed in³⁹, must be done in order to obtain the
347 perceptual solution of the images, independently of the algorithms being judged.

348

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